

Perception of Secondary School Teachers on Artificial Intelligence and Indigenous Education in Ogun East Senatorial District, Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract: There is a preference for Western education over Indigenous Education to train children in Nigeria. This development which has led to sacrificing cultural vocations is not peculiar to a particular ethnic group in Nigeria but every tribe in Nigeria is culpable. The corollary of this, apart from all else, is that traits such as honesty, respect for elders, communalism, hard work, and perseverance, among others have been declining among Nigerian youths today. The introduction of the internet, generally, and Artificial Intelligence, particularly, has impacted every area of human life, including the capacity to perform tasks that were typically associated with human intelligence. In the area of education, Artificial Intelligence can be used to enhance and promote Indigenous Education in Nigeria due to its efficiency and acceptability among Nigerian youths. Against this background, this paper examines the nexus between Artificial Intelligence and Indigenous Education in Nigeria. The study utilised a survey research design with three (3) research questions as a guide. Convenience sampling technique was used to select the respondents i.e. two hundred (200) Civic education and English language teachers in government-owned Secondary Schools in Ogun East Senatorial District of Ogun State, Nigeria. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics of simple percentage and t-test. Findings from the study revealed among others that Artificial Intelligence can influence Indigenous Education in fundamental ways if the impediments facing its integration into Indigenous Education can be addressed. The study concluded that since Artificial Intelligence is one of the means through which Indigenous Education can be facilitated and promoted, stakeholders in the education sector should ensure that it is incorporated into Indigenous Education and vice versa and that cultural vocations and value systems should be made relevant at schools in Nigeria.

Keywords: Perception, Artificial Intelligence, Indigenous Education

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is a country of about 522 local languages with significant impact on the cultural values and relations in the country (Akindele, Oladepo & Akano, 2022). These are transmitted from one generation to the other in various informal forms before the contact with Europeans and imposition of colonial rule. According to Adamu and Rotshak (2023), Nigeria had its form of education prior to the advent of the British colonialists; each and every community within its territorial borders had its modes of passing its rich cultural heritage to the upcoming generation. The patterns and modes of inculcating these cultural values – honesty, respect, hard work, perseverance, etc. – involves a series of skilfully crafted approaches through which knowledge is transferred from the elders in the community to the younger generation.

Indigenous education has been used interchangeably as African traditional education in research efforts and according to Marah (2006), African traditional education had a means that was intertwined with the social, cultural, artistic, religious and recreational life of the people. This is ‘schooling’ since it empowers the people with the pertinent knowledge of their existential realities. The knowledge of indigenous education is imperative in this age and time due to the fact that it has the capability of serving as the basis upon which knowledge is acquired through digital sources and can be well integrated for the benefit of society at large.

The artificial intelligence revolution currently going on has not by-passed the field of education. This is apt due to the unprecedented technological advancement in the field of education and the aspect of language learning in particular. According to Chen, Chen & Lin (2020), artificial intelligence has increased the efficacy of management and instruction. Artificial intelligence, according to Makanjuola-Agbola and Solomon (2023) refers to designing machines to make them behave like humans in terms of reasoning and processing of information. To Nwankunor (2021), artificial intelligence is the computer-controlled robots that think intelligibly like humans as these robots are controlled electronically with the aid of the computer by mimicking the competencies of the human mind. Artificial intelligence is both a driving force of the forth educational revolution and a major carrier of the technological progress that is changing societies and economies globally (Verma, 2018).

According to Asak and Asak (2025), AI driven solutions have the potential to create adaptive learning environments that respond to real life learners' progress, preferences and challenges. With the use of sophisticated data analysis and machine learning algorithms, these systems tend to yield insights that were previously unattainable, thereby; supporting not only the acquisition of grammar but also the development of critical communicative competencies (Wang, Wang, Zhu, Wang, Tran & Du, 2024). With the establishment of the National Agency for Research in Robotics and Artificial Intelligence (NARRAI) in 2018, the Nigerian government has taken a decisive step in promoting the advancement of artificial intelligence. Against this backdrop, this paper examines perception on artificial intelligence and indigenous education in Nigeria, using teachers in government-owned secondary schools in Ogun East Senatorial District of Ogun State as a study focus.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There is a growing preference for formal education over indigenous education in Nigeria - a disturbing situation which has further made the younger generation derail from the ethics, norms, ethos and culture of our forebears. Traits in Nigerian cultures such as honesty, respect for elders, communalism, hard work, and perseverance, among others have been eroded by the wide embrace of foreign cultural practices introduced during colonialism and further entrenched through neo-colonialism. Scholars in the field of indigenous education have written widely but their research efforts have not adequately looked into the influence of Artificial Intelligence and this lacuna gives impetus for this research effort. Secondary school teachers were utilised in this study due to the fact that they are closer to students who meant to understand the immense benefits of indigenous education.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Identify the influence of AI on indigenous education in Nigeria;
2. ascertain the challenges militating against the integration of AI on indigenous education; and
3. determine ways through which AI can enhance indigenous education.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How do the respondents perceive the influence of AI on indigenous education?

2. What are the challenges facing the integration of AI into indigenous education?
3. In what ways can AI enhance indigenous education?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilised a survey research design with three (3) research questions as a guide. The population consisted of all English language and Civic education teachers in Ogun State, Nigeria. Convenience sampling technique was used to select the respondents, i.e. two hundred (200) Civic education and English language teachers in government-owned Secondary Schools in Ogun East Senatorial District of Ogun State, Nigeria. The research instruments were Questionnaire on Perceptions of AI in Indigenous Education (QPAIE) with five (5) items; Questionnaire on Challenges of Integrating AI into Indigenous Education (QCIAIE) with five (5) items; and Questionnaire on Future Prospects (QFP) with ten (10) items. The set of questionnaire was administered by the first/corresponding author. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics of simple percentage, mean and standard deviation.

Data Presentation and Discussion of Findings

DATA PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1: How do the respondents perceive the influence of AI on indigenous education?

Table 1: Perception of the Respondents on the Influence of AI on Indigenous Education

Items	SA(%)	A(%)	D(%)	SD(%)	Mean	Sd
Artificial Intelligence can be effectively integrated into African indigenous educational systems.	36(14.4)	171(68.4)	32(12.8)	11(4.4)	2.93	.667
AI has the potential to enhance the preservation and transmission of indigenous knowledge.	109(43.6)	109(43.6)	11(4.4)	21(8.4)	3.22	.877
Incorporating AI into indigenous education can improve student engagement and learning outcomes.	48(19.2)	138(55.2)	11(4.4)	53(21.2)	2.72	1.006
AI tools can be adapted to support the teaching of indigenous languages.	121(48.4)	87(34.8)	22(8.8)	20(8.0)	3.24	.916
The use of AI in education aligns with the cultural values and practices of African communities.	130(52.0)	90(36.0)	10(4.0)	20(8.0)	3.32	.884
Mean aggregate = 3.06, SD = 0.25						

Table 1 shows the perception of the respondents on the influence of AI on indigenous education. From the table, all the items are structured positively and SA and A have higher percentages when combined ranging between 74.4% and 88.0%. It follows that the majority of the respondents have positive perception about the influence of AI on indigenous education. The mean aggregate; 3.06 which is greater than the mean benchmark; 2.5 confirms this result. This finding is in consonance with the work of Marah (2006) which asserts that in the digital age, African traditional education can serve as the pillar upon which knowledge is acquired digitally and can be closely linked for societal benefits. Also, Asak and Asak (2025) affirm that artificial intelligence assumes an important role in language education by facilitating specialised learning experiences, providing instant feedback and providing an expansive repository of linguistic resources.

Research Question 2: What are the challenges facing the integration of AI into indigenous education?

Table 2: Challenges Facing the Integration of AI into Indigenous Education

Items	SA(%)	A(%)	D(%)	SD(%)	Mean	Sd
Limited access to technological infrastructure hinders the implementation of AI in indigenous educational settings.	81(32.4)	108(43.2)	20(8.0)	41(16.4)	2.92	1.028
There is a lack of culturally relevant AI educational content tailored to African indigenous contexts.	89(35.6)	131(52.4)	11(4.4)	19(7.6)	3.16	.825
Educators in indigenous communities face challenges in acquiring the necessary skills to utilise AI tools effectively.	110(44.0)	91(36.4)	29(11.6)	20(8.0)	3.16	.923
The cost of implementing AI technologies is a significant barrier for indigenous educational institutions.	67(26.8)	111(44.4)	51(20.4)	21(8.4)	2.90	.895
Concerns about data privacy and security impede the adoption of AI in indigenous education.	80(32.0)	121(48.4)	9(3.6)	40(16.0)	2.96	.999
Mean aggregate = 3.02, SD = 0.13						

Table 2 reveals the challenges facing the integration of AI into indigenous education. From the table, all the items are structured negatively and SA and A have higher percentages when combined ranging between 71.2% and 88.6%. It follows that majority of the respondents agreed that all the stated items are the challenges facing the integration of AI into indigenous education. The mean aggregate; 3.02 which is greater than the mean benchmark; 2.5 confirms this result. This finding agrees with the finding of Mgbomo and Nkaanee (2025) which state that the impediments facing the integration of artificial intelligence into indigenous education are infrastructural deficits, digital divide and inequality, limited digital literacy on the sides of both students and teachers, high costs of artificial intelligence implementation, ethical and privacy concerns, and resistance to change and lack of awareness on the part of stereotyped teachers, administrators and other policy makers in the education sector. In the same vein, Ukala and Ukala (2024) are of the view that there is constant power interruption in Nigeria which is capable of hindering constant artificial intelligence usage.

There is also the rural-urban disparity that may arise if artificial intelligence remains concentrated in unity and flagship schools (Tang & Su, 2024). Edinoh, Onah & Ogunbowale (2025) affirm that most artificial intelligence systems are developed with a broad, global audience in mind, and often neglecting the unique cultural, linguistic and educational contexts of some regions such as Nigeria.

Research Question 3: In what ways can AI enhance indigenous education?

Table 3: Prospects of AI in Enhancing Indigenous Education

Items	SA(%)	A(%)	D(%)	SD(%)	Mean	Sd
AI can help preserve and promote indigenous languages through translation and speech tools.	98(39.2)	91(36.4)	40(16.0)	21(8.4)	3.06	.942
The integration of AI into indigenous education will improve access to quality learning resources.	132(52.8)	90(36.0)	9(3.6)	19(7.6)	3.34	.869
AI has the potential to support personalized learning for indigenous students.	76(30.4)	135(54.0)	19(7.6)	20(8.0)	3.07	.836
AI technologies can help document indigenous knowledge and cultural heritage effectively.	82(32.8)	139(55.6)	19(7.6)	10(4.0)	3.17	.733
Teachers in indigenous communities can benefit from AI-powered teaching aids and lesson planning tools.	67(26.8)	153(61.2)	21(8.4)	9(3.6)	3.11	.697

AI can bridge the gap between traditional learning methods and modern education systems.	91(36.4)	113(45.2)	37(14.8)	9(3.6)	3.14	.799
The use of AI in indigenous education may lead to cultural erosion.	80(32.0)	143(57.2)	18(7.2)	9(3.6)	3.18	.712
With proper guidance, AI can enhance indigenous students' interest and performance in school.	101(40.4)	108(43.2)	10(4.0)	31(12.4)	3.12	.965
Mean aggregate = 3.15, SD =0.09						

Table 3 reveals the prospects of AI in enhancing indigenous education. All the items are structured positively, and SA and A have higher percentages when combined ranging between 75.6% and 89.2%. It follows that the majority of the respondents agreed that all the stated items are the prospects of AI in enhancing indigenous education. The mean aggregate; 3.15 which is greater than the mean benchmark; 2.5 confirms this result. This finding agrees with that of Holmes et al. (2019) which state that personalised learning technologies (AI) enhance students' engagement and performance by addressing unique learning challenges. More so, Mgbomo and Nkaanee (2025) have it that artificial intelligence can facilitate data-driven decision making exercises by analysing large datasets to identify trends and predict students' learning outcomes. Adesina (2021) is of the view that AI-based distance learning solutions played a veritable role in sustaining education during the Covid-19 necessitated lockdown in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence undoubtedly has the potential to revolutionise indigenous education in Nigeria. It is no longer news that Nigeria is at a crossroads, especially about indigenous education that is constantly on the decline in recent times due to preference for formal classroom education. Since there are two sides to a coin, it is either we allow our rich cultural heritage (indigenous education) to be wiped off under our watchful eyes, or a joint effort is made to sustain our rich cultural values. The latter would be championed in order to further pass on the traits of honesty, respect for elders, communalism, hard work, and perseverance to the younger generations and make the society a better place for all – irrespective of age, gender, religion and cultural affiliations. For this to happen, rather than abandon traditional education, artificial intelligence can be integrated into traditional education and vice versa.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Cultural vocations and value systems should be made relevant at schools by the ministries of education (state and federal).
2. Government, ministries of education, school administrators and other key stakeholders in the education sector should form public-private partnerships in order to provide adequate

- funding, resources and expertise in artificial intelligence education ingenuity at schools in Nigeria.
3. AI should be utilised in preserving and promoting indigenous languages and cultural identities.
 4. Parents and guardians, as a matter of necessity, should emphasise the importance of cultural values inherent in indigenous education with their children/wards.

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